

A STUDY ON MENTAL HEALTH AND STUDY HABIT OF ORPHAN CHILDREN LIVING IN ORPHANAGES.

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The purpose of this study was to find out the correlation between the mental health and study habit. The samples were selected by the purposive sampling technique. A total of 60 orphan students (Govt. orphanage -30, SOS -30) between the age group of 12-18 years were undertaken. The research tool used for mental health was developed by Dr. JAGDISH and SRIVASTAVA (1983), while the tool for study habits was developed by Dr. LAJWANTI, Prof .N.P.S. CHANDEL and Mr. Paliwal (2013). Here 't' test was applied to check the significance of mental health and study habit in students. To check relation between mental health and study habit correlation was used.

Failure to detect one's mental health problems may result in negative and hazardous consequences such as increasable risks for academic failure, social isolation, drug and alcohol abuse, depression, low self-esteem, short temper, suicide attempt, unemployment, poor mental health and overall loss (mosdhyedi, 2008).

Results revealed that low level of correlation is present between mental health and study habit of orphan children's while there was significance differences in between mental health and study habit of government orphanage and SOS Children village.

Key-words: MENTAL HEALTH, STUDY HABIT, ORPHAN.

INTRODUCTION

An orphan is defined as a child under the age of 18 years whose mother, father, or both biological parents have died (including those whose living status is reported as unknown, but excluding those whose living status is unspecified (Helen Meintjes & Katharine Hall, 2012). An orphanage is an institution meant for providing care and protection to orphan children. Thousands of children are made orphans due to several reasons. Orphan children are growing up in orphanages, without love and care. The children receive food, clothes, education and roof over their heads but they never get the love support of family, which is critical to a child's healthy development. Without it children suffer great harm and deeply damaged. Mental health is concerned with balanced state of mind. A person must be free from stress, tensions, conflicts, confusions, depression, etc. A person must have a problem solving attitude, he should be able to

think about right or wrong, etc. "Mental health is a state of well-being in which the individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully and is able to make a contribution to his or her community" (World Health Organization,2001). "Mental health is the foundation for well-being and effective functioning for an individual and community. It is more than the absence of mental illness; it is a resource vital to individuals, families and societies" (British Columbia, Ministry of Health, 2007). Mental health is a balance between all aspect of life-social, physical, spiritual and emotional aspect of a person. It imparts on how we manage our surroundings and make choices in our overall health (Negi, 2010). Study habit is a important factor in learning.

Objective of the Study:

The main objective of the study was as under:

1. To measure the Mental Health of children residing in Govt. orphanages and SOS Children village.
2. To measure the Study Habit of children residing in Govt. orphanages and SOS Children village.
3. To measure the co-relation between Mental Health and Study Habit.

Hypothesis of the Study:

H₁. The significance difference in Mental Health of children residing in Govt. orphanages and SOS Children village

H₂. The significance difference in Study Habit of children residing in Govt. orphanages and SOS Children village.

H₃ The significance co-relation between Mental Health and Study Habit.

RESEARCH METHOD:

In the present study, researcher selected Orphan Homes run by Government of Chhattisgarh and NGOs of Raipur district (Chhattisgarh).

SAMPLE:

The sample was selected by the purposive sampling technique. A total of 60 orphan students (Govt. orphanage -30, SOS Children village. -30) between the age group of 12-18 years were undertaken.

TOOL:

The research tool for mental health was developed by Dr. JAGDISH and SRIVASTAVA (1983), while the tool for study habits was developed by Dr. LAJWANTI, Prof .N.P.S. CHANDEL and Mr. Paliwal (2013).

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES USED:

Here 't' test was applied to check the significance of mental health and study habit in students. To check relation between mental health and study habit correlation was used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**Table-1**

Showing the Mental Health of children residing in Govt. orphanages and SOS Children village.

S.NO.	VARIABLE	N	M	S.D.	t
1	Govt. Orphanages	30	69.53	18.147	6.53
2	SOS Children's village	30	98.57	15.63	

The result obtained on the basic area of mental health reveals significant difference of Govt. orphanages students and SOS Children village living students.

The SOS Children orphan students received higher means score 98.57 as compared to the Govt. orphanages students 69.53. There has mean difference was 29 and Standard Deviation score of SOS orphan students received 18.147 and Govt. orphanage students 15.63. So we can say that study SOS Children village living students have a good mental health than Govt. orphanages students.

The 't' value of mental health was 6.53. There was significance difference between Govt. orphanages and SOS Children village living students.

It means first hypothesis was accepted.

Table-II

Showing the Study Habit of children residing in Govt. orphanages and SOS Children village

S.NO.	VARIABLE	N	M	S.D.	t
1	Govt. Orphanages	30	79.33	8050.63	3.997
2	SOS Children's village	30	94.9	6030.4	

The result obtained on the basic area of Study Habit reveals significant difference of Govt. orphanages and SOS Children village living students.

The SOS Children orphan students received higher means score 94.9 as compared to the Govt. orphanages students 79.33. There has mean difference was 14.67 and the standard deviation score of SOS orphan students received 6030.4 and Govt. orphanage students 8050.63. The 't' value of Study Habit was 3.997. There was significant difference among Govt. orphanages and SOS Children village living students in Mental Health. So we can say that better study habits in and SOS Children village living students rather than Govt. orphanages students.

It means second hypothesis was accepted.

Table-III

Showing the significance co-relation between Mental Health and Study Habit

S.NO.	VARIABLE	N	r	sig
1	MENTAL HEALTH	60	0.21	0.05**
2	STUDY HABIT	60		

The result obtained that there is high positive co-relation between Mental Health and Study Habit.

The **0.21** is low positive correlation between mental health and study habit. Mental health is a very important factor that students have good mental health his/her study habit has good.

It means third hypothesis was accepted.

CONCLUSION:

There was significance difference found in mental health of govt. orphanage and SOS children villages' .study shows that children from govt. orphanage and their study habits are better too because of that. Our study concluded that better mental health result in better study habits. The differences in mental health and study habits of both orphanages are due to present of difference in atmosphere of both orphanages. Amenities available to children , food provided to than & behaviors of orphanages officials directly affects both mental health and study habits of children's residing in them.

With help of results shown in our study we can inspire orphanages officials to take care of each child according to their mental states, for improvement of environment of orphanages various seminar and workshop and appointment of regular counselor can be arranged which will be directly beneficial to their mental health and improve their study habits.

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